

& Mycology lab - Via del Borghetto 80 - 56124 Pisa, Italy. E-mail: moncini@crisba.eu

Cereals quality can be affected, during storage, by pests or mycotoxicogenic fungi. The use of controlled atmosphere, with O₂ replaced by N₂, represents a promising tool to reduce cereals crop losses in post harvest. Aim of the present work is to evaluate a system – patented by Eurosider sas – to maintain qualitative and quantitative features of cereals grain by their storage under a highly purified N₂ controlled atmosphere. The project consists in different parallel lab-scale experiments aimed to assess the effect of N₂ atmosphere on: i) growth and mycotoxin production by mycotoxicogenic fungi, such as *Fusarium verticillioides*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium langsethiae* and *Fusarium graminearum*, on corn and wheat; ii) growth and reproduction of two of the most important post harvest pests such as *Sitophilus* sp. and *Tribolium* sp.; iii) qualitative parameters of corn. The use of highly purified N₂ controlled atmosphere significantly affects growth and sporulation of *F. verticillioides* and *A. flavus*, fumonisin and aflatoxin producers respectively, and of *F. graminearum* e *F. langsethiae*, DON and T2 and HT2 producers respectively. Atmosphere containing 95.0% and 98.5% N₂ caused, in wheat, the complete mortality of adult population of *Sitophilus* sp. after 12 and 6 days, respectively. This last result was confirmed for *Tribolium* sp. Qualitative parameters, and mainly umidity and *Total Antioxidant Capacity*, were positively affected in corn. These positive preliminary results prompt us to scale up the system, to assess its efficacy in controlling cereals grain crop losses in larger silos.

68. THE H2020 PONTE PROJECT WEB SITE: AN ONLINE RESOURCE FOR SCIENTIFIC DISSEMINATION ON EMERGING PEST DISEASES. M. Morelli¹, M. Saponari¹, D. Tavano¹, D. Boscia¹, A. Obradović². ¹CNR Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante (IPSP), SS Bari, 70126 Bari, Italy. ²University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture, 11080 Belgrade, Serbia. E-mail: massimiliano.morelli@ipsp.cnr.it.

The International Research Consortium POnTE (Pest Organism Threatening Europe) is being funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme to investigate four pathogens (i.e. *Xylella fastidiosa*, *Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum*, *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus* and *Phytophthora* spp.) representing a major threat to strategic crops and natural landscapes in the EU, and to identify integrated management strategies for their containment. The wide range of studies conducted within the Project tasks on key emergent pests and the rising request for accessing up-to-date references over the Internet, suggested the need to provide a larger variety of real-time information about the project and its targets for a much wider variety of end-users. A WordPress-based web portal (www.ponteproject.eu) has been created by the Coordination Team to support collaborative platform functions, enhance the project's visibility and provide in a flexible manner a rapid dissemination of valuable information, fostering raise of general knowledge and public awareness on relevant themes in plant pathology. Answering to the modern challenges, accounting for an effective web-based pest information system, the resource is intended as an open-access platform to share scientific achievements, upload promotional material and fact sheets, communicate conferences and training courses, report press review and legislative regulations. A social media presence on Twitter and Facebook channels was set up from the early stages in order to enable a two-way communication with a web-active audience and work towards a continuous engagement of the major plant pathology networking platforms and institutional accounts. To keep Project partners and interested parties always informed of the web site updates and encourage frequent visits, a newsletter is being released on a weekly basis.

69. WILTING LEAVES OF EGGPLANT CAUSED BY PSEUDOMONAS SYRINGAE IN ITALY. C. Moretti¹, G. Caranante², V.M. Stravato², R. Buonaurio¹. ¹Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari e Ambientali (DSA3) - University of Perugia, Borgo XX Giugno 74 - 06121 Perugia, Italy. ²GENISTA s.r.l., via San Vincenzo 13 - 04022 Fondi (LT), Italy. E-mail: chiara.luce.moretti@unipg.it

In March 2015, eggplants (*Solanum melongena* L.) cv. Angela, grown in Terracina (Latium, Italy) under plastic, showed severe wilting symptoms with an incidence of about 40%. The symptoms, which started from the basal leaves, were sometimes unilateral and led to leaf blight. The plants showing such symptoms were stunted and no vascular discolorations were observed. Whitish bacterial colonies were consistently isolated from the diseased stem/leaf tissues. Two representative selected strains, which were gram negative, fluorescent on King's medium B, and had oxidative but not fermentative metabolism, were subjected to pathogenicity test by inoculating eggplant seedlings at 4th-5th leaf stage. Blackening of the stem above and, at less extent, under the inoculation point was observed 4-5 days after the inoculation, and bacteria with the same cultural features of the original strains were re-isolated from inoculated plants. For bacterial identification, the strains were subjected to LOPAT tests. They were levan positive, oxidase negative, potato rot negative, arginine dihydrolase negative, and tobacco hypersensitive response positive, indicating that they belonged to Lelliot's LOPAT group 1. When 16S rDNA gene sequences were compared by BLASTn with nucleotide sequences from GenBank, they showed 93% identity with the comparable sequences of *Pseudomonas syringae*. In a MLST approach, four housekeeping genes (*gltA*, *gap1*, *gyrB* and *rpoD*) were sequenced and the phylogenetic tree was built based on concatenated sequences. This analysis revealed that the two eggplant isolates and the strains PSC1B of *P. syringae* pv. *syringae* from corn were identical. Further analyses are in progress to confirm whether the bacterium belong to the *syringae* pathovar.

70. THE PLANT PROTECTION PRODUCTS DATABASE (Mi.PAAF). C. Morgia, F. Milano, A. Santacaterina, A. Matrone, S. Rosati, L. Donnarumma. *Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria, Centro di Ricerca per la Patologia Vegetale, Via C.G. Bertero, 22 - 00156 Roma, Italy. E-mail: cinzia.morgia@crea.gov.it*

The Plant Protection Products Database of Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry Policies (Mi.PAAF), managed by the CREA-Plant Pathology Research Center, has been active for more than 15 years and is a complete information system that provides quick upgrade to agricultural technicians and operators in crop protection. The Plant Protection Products and Active Substances Database is a reference tool for workers in the Rural Network, particularly in the areas of agriculture, agribusiness, floriculture: it provides detailed and updated information on plant protection products for field, vegetable, horticulture and fruit crops as well as ornamentals (more than 15.000 forms). Moreover, Maximum Residue Limits (MRLs) allowed on active substances authorized in agriculture at the national level are listed. The database management, the update in real time and the computer program based on, have been the object of an innovative action and expansion of the system for the best use. In the 2014-2015, it was put in place an effective audit and management of the database in accordance with the needs of users and the actions planned by the National Action Plan for integrated pest management. The work shows this innovative action founded by Mi.PAAF.